

Reaction of Tartaric Acid with Sodium Molybdate and Sodium Tungstate

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Tartaric acid is known to form complexes with a number of elements, e.g., silver¹, magnesium, calcium², strontium³, beryllium⁴, etc. It is also used to separate tungsten and molybdenum⁵. The authors while studying the complex formation of sodium molybdate and sodium tungstate with certain organic acids like mandelic acid⁶ and lactic acid⁷, took up the reaction of tartaric acid with sodium molybdate and sodium tungstate by employing physico-chemical methods like conductance and *pH*.

Procedure.—B. D. H. AnalR samples of sodium molybdate and sodium tungstate were taken and were analysed by the usual methods. The analyses corresponded to the formulae, $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. Tartaric acid of E. Merck quality was used. The solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Conductance and *pH* measurements were performed with the help of Doran's conductivity bridge and Beckman's *pH* meter respectively. All the solutions were kept in an electrically maintained thermostat at $28^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

To a constant amount of sodium tungstate and sodium molybdate varying amounts of tartaric acid were added; the total volume was made up to a constant volume each time. The solutions were kept overnight to attain equilibrium and then *pH* and conductance of the solutions were measured. Graphs were plotted between the physical properties and the amount of ligand added. Three sets of measurements were performed with *M*/15, *M*/20, and *M*/30 solutions. A clear break was obtained in every case which corresponded to the ratio 1:1 for both sodium molybdate and sodium tungstate.

To confirm the above conclusion recourse was taken to Job's method of continued variation. In this case both the solutions of equal strength were taken and various sets of solutions were prepared, always keeping the total strength constant. Measurements of conductance were performed with three different concentrations, viz., *M*/80, *M*/100, and

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5. Welcher, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Vol. II, 1955, D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., New York, p. 182.

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M/120. In all cases graphs were plotted between the divergence from the additivity rule against the percentage of the ligand used. Every time a maximum was obtained at 50% which evidently established the stoichiometry of the above complexes at 1:1.

Experiments are in progress to find out the value of the dissociation constants of the above complexes and to establish their structure by studying the above with properly substituted acids.

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